

Project delivery 1: Selection of AI-software

Introduction

The overall aim of this project is to investigate the extent different artificial intelligence (AI) software support researchers and students in academic literature search. Our findings will inform future services at the university libraries affiliated to the Royal Library in Denmark.

Support through searching using AI-powered technologies can be provided in a multitude of ways – through saving time, through searching more efficiently and effectively, through providing new avenues of discovery and through transparency and documentation. However, support will be actively investigated, analyzed and discussed later in the project. We have a working hypothesis in the project that different types of user (student, senior researchers and library staff) place different values on different types of support. In this first delivery, we state how AI-powered search is actually defined within the confines of the project, and which AI software will be included for further testing and why.

Definition of AI software

In the context of our project AI-powered search software is defined as:

“Search software that learns from the user to deliver the next best action, and the capability of the system to auto-tune results based on what it learns from users.”

Norbert Krupa,
Lucidworks Senior Solutions Engineer
(Florez, 2019)

This means that AI-powered searching software included in this project use labour saving features known as building blocks, individually or in combination. These building blocks are:

Aggregated behaviour: an aggregated search interface is designed to integrate search results from different sources (web, image, video, blog, etc) into a single result page (Arguello, 2017). The search algorithm learns from the users interaction with the displayed results (a subset of machine learning). Aggregated behaviour such as click-throughs, conversions, and queries teach the engine which content is most relevant. The more data available to an AI-powered search engine, the more relevant results it can return to a user. (Florez, 2019)

Recommendations: the AI-powered search weighs models of the users' search behaviour, in addition to other similar users' behaviour, location, and more, to calculate and present the most relevant results. (Florez, 2019)

Semantic search: provides domain-specific understanding of what users are typing in and what those words mean within each user's query and context (a sub-set of Natural Language Processing). The focus is on the meaning behind search queries instead of the traditional keyword matching (Picánek, 2020). Semantic Knowledge Graphs enable the engine to understand entities and lexical hierarchies, embrace ambiguity, disambiguate phrases with multiple potential meanings, and to gain a nuanced understanding of the user's intent in order to perform a conceptual search (Picánek, 2020; Florez, 2019).

Clustering and classification techniques: train the search engine to understand different words that can be a part of the same category and display search results as semantically similar topic-groups of references that the user can filter down to increase specificity (Florez, 2019; Iris.ai, 2018a).

Background to the project

The initial project application was written in Danish, hence in the following, a brief recap of the motivation for the project is presented in English. A clear understanding of the motivation for the project, informs the rationale for our decisions to include and exclude AI software and sets the context for the experimental design.

Our project builds on lessons learned from an innovation trip to Helsinki in December 2019. The aim of the trip was to gain knowledge about how AI-powered search was being implemented in researcher support by University Libraries and research support centers. Particularly, tests by the University of Helsinki with the product Iris.ai (Iris.ai, 2018b) had caught the attention of our library leaders.

AI-powered searching is a strategic focus of future researcher support strategies at the university libraries/Royal Library in Denmark. The aim is to integrate AI-powered search in teaching and support services. AI has the potential to analyze a great amount of complex data and through the use of mathematical formula and machine learning, make decisions and solve problems more quickly and precisely than the human searcher can do. At the library however, we first need to learn more about the potentials of AI search technology in order to be able to critically appraise AI search products, their usefulness, drawbacks and potential. Only then can we confidently develop new and effective services devoted to AI-powered search.

Our visit to Helsinki taught us that AI-powered search software is relatively new and constantly being improved and adapted to different search environments and user requirements. A testing period over two or three years is recommended to give a fair assessment of the value of the product for the university. Currently, AI-powered search has a greater potential in the hard sciences, where publications are primarily in English, in the form of articles rather than monographs, are widely available via Open Access and are stored in well-structured database architecture that employ international indexing standards/ontologies. Therefore, a good discipline to start testing AI-powered search software on is the Health Sciences, particularly in the support of systematic review development. Finally, we are aware that there are many AI-powered software on the market, some free and open source, others subscription with the possibility in paid premium versions to tailor the product to fit

the needs of the user. Thus, we will attempt an assessment of both free and paid AI-powered search software to learn more about if you get what you pay for in regards to functionalities, declared permissions, and their data collection behaviours and privacy practices.

It is essential that tools and software promoted by the library can be used to support the responsible conduct of research and implemented to support research integrity. This means that any AI tool supporting the search, free or paid, must also support the responsible conduct of research, fx provide possibilities for methodological transparency, support validity, reliability, reproducibility and good citation practice. No unnecessary data about the user of the software or any other tracking data may be collected without consent.

Logically, the background and considerations concerning research integrity lead to a list of requirements to AI-powered search software, as described in the next section.

List of requirements

AI-powered search software included in this project must:

- use one or more of the building blocks of AI-powered search
- be designed to support academic literature search
- be designed to support discovery of related literature/concepts
- be available for testing over a 2-3 year period
- be suitable for application in full text resources, databases of references and abstracts in the health science disciplines
- have clear policies and permissions regarding data collection behaviours and privacy practices
- support the responsible conduct of research, such as providing functionalities supporting methodological transparency, reproducibility and good citation practice, including documentation of the applied search and ranking/clustering algorithms.

AI-powered software considered in the project

A complete overview of AI-powered search software considered for inclusion in the project as well as links to each product and documentation files is presented in Appendix 1. In the table below a digest of information is presented.

Software	About											
Iris.ai	Search OA literature & topic modelling. Can be tailored to include chosen sources. Uses AI/ML/NLP, fingerprinting, and data modelling.											
	Support Search*	Domain	Free/Paid	Desktop/Web	Multi-user	Maturity	Difficulty level	Help	Registration	Inc.	Ex.	Rationale
	Yes	Health, Chemistry	Free for individual users, though limited functionality. Paid version (individual license or organisation)	Both	Yes -paid version only	Stable	Low.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Product supports academic search using AI
Microsoft Academic	About											
	Data sources in BING accessed through APIs and the Open Academic Society. Uses semantic search, ML, NLP, basic filters (author, journal, field of study). Compile a leaderboard of the most cited scientists in each sub-discipline. Designed to support literature reviews											
	Yes	All	Free	Web	No	Stable	Easy	Yes	Voluntary but beneficial	Yes	No	Supports searching. Unclear how AI is used and how to document the search and interpret the search algorithm.
Omnia	About											
	Enables search for the “combination” or “intersection” of Paper 1 and Paper 2. Uses blockchain technology for commercial research and development to compare semantic language or actual meaning of content to reveal patterns and connections. Multilingual search.											
	Yes	All	Public: Free Enterprise: Paid	Web	-	No product development since 2015	Low	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes – if product is still supported
Semantic Scholar	About											
	Developed for researchers by researchers. Scan research output through automatic identification of abstracts, tables, figures and citations; Uses citation statistics to assess impact; Finds related data on GitHub plus other materials that add context. Advanced filtering, focus on specific publications and disciplines. Sorts results after papers, citations, relevance and importance.											
	Yes	computer science and neuroscience	Free	Web	No	From 2015, stable and under development	Low	Yes	Voluntary but beneficial	Yes	No	Uses AI-powered search –learn more about how to interpret search algorithms.
Yewno	About											
	Search using ideas and concepts rather than keywords. Integrates with other discovery services to develop questions in research projects. Search in academic or government documents in English, German or Chinese. Full-text analysis through the use of computational semantics, neural networks, & Machine-Learning. Graphic display of results (concept map - orange nodes = important concepts, blue nodes = ideas, related to the concepts; & context bar). Links to resources by clicking on the nodes											
	Yes	All	Paid	Web	-	Stable	-	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Designed to support search and discovery using AI-powered technology
	About											
	User- interface to search multiple sources one at a time. Reference manager functionality, where the user can save documents in project folders with easy export possibilities. Lab productivity tools. Write & cite integration for WORD. Access publications at the lowest possible price, pay as you go, link to content the user has subscription to, OA content, remove duplicates and explanations of copywrite.											

Article Galaxy	Yes	All specifically hard sciences and biomedicine	Free	Web	no	new gadgets regularly added	Low	Yes	<u>Yes</u>	No	Yes	Doesn't support searching. Supports access to literature.
Connected Papers	About Visualizes connections between documents, to give overview of an academic area, using citations and bibliographic coupling. Compatible with Semantic Scholar, PubMed, Paper Title, arXiv and paperDOI. Links to user's ORCID.											
	Yes	All	Free	Web	no	Stable	Low	Minimal	Voluntary but beneficial	No	Yes	Does not support the search. Chases one DOI or URL at a time.
DistillerAI	About Sort and rank references w.r.t. probability they will be included in a review. Functions as part of review/screening process, and highlights references that mistakenly have been excluded. The user uploads references or a PubMed query to a design screening template. In DistillerAI, the user searches in their "coded" references.											
	No	All	Paid, 3 month free trial by request.	-	Yes (paid version only)	Stable	Low	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Does not support the search.
Google Scholar	About Advanced and simple keyword searches in Google's collection of scholarly literature											
	Yes	All	Free	Web	No	Stable	Low	Yes	Not a demand. Google Scholar profile makes the users profile more visible on the internet.	No	Yes	Suspected not AI-powered search. No clear documentation
IBM Watson	About Business intelligence - investigate data in new ways, uses AI applications and tool, fx Watson Discover (prediction models, infor decisions, optimize workflows), knowledge Studio, Drug Discovery. Packages of different AI solutions. For industry, IT packages for operations, customer services, inc. packages i IT operations, customer service, risk & compliance and finance. Watson Natural Language Understanding, is a cloud native product that uses deep learning to extract metadata from text such as entities, keywords, categories, sentiment, emotion, relations, and syntax.											
	No	industry/enterprise	Paid (agree on a financial plan)	Both plus cloud	Unknown	Stable	High	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Does not support or provide AI-powered search for literature
Sparrho	About Uses SoMe model to function as personalized recommendation system. Searches articles, grants, patents, conference papers. NLP, tracks users - what they share, read and save. Functions as a "pinboard" where the user marks what they are interested in and then recieves notations when news on the topics they are interested in pops up.											

	No	All, mostly science	Free	Web	No	Under development	Low	Minimal	Yes	No	Yes	Does not support search
Unsiilo	About											
	Products for publishers and business and tech solutions for stakeholders in academia and the life sciences. NLP & APIs used to find, connect and share content. "Determined to make it easier for researchers and innovators to find analogous concepts and novel ideas from different industries and fields."											
	No	Business, tech and hard sciences	Paid	Web	-	Under development	-	-	Yes	No	Yes	Does not support search
Keenoious	About											
	Analyses entire text and browses through millions of articles, papers, and studies on the web to find the most relevant information in seconds. Highlight a sentence or paragraph in your document to identify related literature using AI technology. Ai is used to analyze the content and style of the written work, Integerates with Word (Google docs in development)											
	Yes	All	Free, with Microsoft account	Both	-	Under development	Low	No	No	No	Yes	No. Searches automatically in Microsoft Academic. A plug-in to Word. Tracking issues
Annif	About											
	Assigns subject headings for new documents. Tool for automated subject indexing and classification using a combination of NLP and ML including Maui, Omikuji, fastText and Gensim. It is multilingual and can support any subject vocabulary (in SKOS or a simple TSV format). It provides a command-line interface, a simple Web UI and a microservice-style REST API.											
	No	All	Free	Web	No	Stable	Llow	Yes.	No	No	Yes	The product supports the indexing process not the search process
Hamlet (MIT)	About											
	Uses machine learning to power experimental, exploratory interfaces to the MIT thesis collection. Plug in a thesis and find out which other theses are most conceptually similar.											
	No	MIT theses database	Free		No	stable	Low	Yes	No	No	Yes	Does not support the search for academic literature outside of the MIT database
Carrot2	About											
	Clustering machine that sorts and displays the search results in folders and clusters. There are a variety of clustering algorithms to choose from.											
	Minimal	All, plus PubMed	Free	Web	No	Constant development	Low	Yes	no	Yes	no	Very similar to Iris.ai. Needs further investigation

*The search can be a structured approach or a quick and dirty search

The search for AI-powered search products was undertaken in the period May 2020 to September 2020. Software was found by searching the internet and through contact with partners at libraries also investigating the use of AI-powered search. Further, a request for information about other AI search products not identified in our search was posted on the mailinglist Expert Searching in September 2020. The search was completed October 1st 2020.

Results of the Preliminary Analysis

The preliminary analysis in Table 1 provided five AI-powered search software for further consideration:

Iris.ai, Microsoft Academic, Carrot2, Semantic Scholar, Omnity and Yewno. Omnity was contacted to verify if the product was still supported. As no reply was received from the company, Omnity was excluded from the project. Accordingly five AI-powered search software are investigated in the project, these are presented below in alphabetic order:

Iris.ai (<https://iris.ai/>)

Iris.ai navigates Open Access literature, primarily in the disciplines of health and chemistry, but also in other sources that can be tailored to fit the users' needs. Topic modelling and "finger printing" technology are used to display results to the user in topic maps, which the user can then filter their way through to increase specificity. Iris.ai offers free and paid versions of the product, that allow to varying degrees, according to negotiation with the vendor, integration with organisational and subscription databases, collaboration and multi-user functionalities, relevance filters, bookmarking, the possibility to establish inclusion and exclusion criteria to the search, import functions and RSS feeds. Iris.ai can be integrated with reference managers and has a surprisingly intuitive approach to search. Demands to the users technical understanding of the programme and supported algorithms are low. Price is after consultation.

Microsoft Academic (<https://academic.microsoft.com/home>)

Microsoft Academic is a free application and a further development of Microsoft Academic Search. Microsoft Academic's data source (Bing) is accessed through an application programming interface (API) and the Open Academic Society. It employs semantic search, basic filters (author, journal, field of study), and can access over 160 million publications, thus has the benefit of being useful for searchers in many different disciplines. It is also possible to compile a leaderboard of the most cited scientists in each subdiscipline. Possibilities to personalise the search environment are under development. The product provides an easy interface to search millions of publications, though little documentation is provided about the search algorithms or how to search appropriately. No registration is required, though if the user does make a profile more functionalities are available such as reading lists, finding related topics and link graphs which can be hooked up to the user's ORCID to increase visibility. The product uses AI (machine learning, natural language processing) and is designed to support literature reviews.

Carrot2 (<https://search.carrot2.org/#/web>)

Carrot2 is a programming library for clustering text. It can automatically discover groups of related documents and label them with short key terms or phrases. It organizes the search results into topics, fully automatically and without external knowledge such as taxonomies or preclassified content. This means there is no common search language as Carrot2 is a meta-search engine. Carrot2 contains two document clustering algorithms designed specifically for search results clustering: Suffix Tree Clustering and Lingo and can cluster content in 19 languages (Danish is one of these). It offers components for fetching data from search engines that provide the required APIs (for example Microsoft Bing or PubMed, Wikipedia), as well as other sources of documents like Lucene, Apache Solr or ElasticSearch. Carrot2 is a community project, non-profit with source code in GitHub. There is the web-based test version, but for full functionality and personalisation install the Carrot2 Document Clustering Workbench, which is a standalone GUI application to experiment with Carrot2 clustering on data from common search engines or the user's own data plus a commandline interface. TheWorkbench is an application that requires advanced instruction and knowledge to be used responsibly.

Semantic Scholar (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/>)

Claiming to be more advanced than Microsoft Academic, Semantic Scholar enables the user to scan research output through automatic identification of abstracts, tables, figures and citations. Specifically, the product is marketed to computer and neuroscience disciplines. It uses traditional citation statistics with semantic analyses to highlight the most important and influential papers, and to identify the connections between them. Other advanced filtering functionalities include focus on specific publications and disciplines, and sorting results after papers, citations, and relevance. Semantic Scholar finds related data on GitHub plus other materials that add context to the results of a search. The product is non-profit, and claims it always will. The demands to users search skills are low, but understanding and interpreting the different algorithms in play can be difficult. Even though documentation is sparse, more information about the product is available after sign in. Creating an account enables the user to create email alerts for new papers, create a library as well as claim an author page so you can better manage your author details and papers.

Yewno (<https://www.yewno.com/>)

Yewno is a multidisciplinary tool that enables the user to search using ideas and concepts rather than keywords. It is designed as a way to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use and frame their work with. Technically, this means that fulltext analysis is conducted through the use of computational semantics, neural networks, & Machine-Learning. In a graphic display of results in a concept map, important nodes of concepts are differentiated from ideas related to the concept. The maps are presented in defined contexts, and change according to the context the user finds most useful. Access to the literature is gained by clicking on the nodes on the map. Yewno can be integrated with the library's other discovery services, and can search in academic or government documents published in English, German or Chinese. Yewno is available as individual or organisation subscription. The price varies according to the package the user has access to. For example a single user account costs \$150 per month whereas the cost of an enterprise account can be negotiated. Each package has helpdesk support and documentation, and information security is a priority.

Requirements fulfillment

Requirements fulfillment focuses on the results of the preliminary analysis. It involves assessment of the objectives of the five AI-systems to fulfill our needs for quality and reliable search tools at the library. The detailed assessment is in Appendix 2, a digest is presented below.

Requirement	Iris.ai	Microsoft Academic	Carrot2	Semantic Scholar	Yewno
use one or more of the building blocks of AI-powered search	Yes	Partial	Yes	Partial	Yes
be designed to support academic literature search	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes
be designed to support discovery of related literature/concepts	Yes	Limited	Yes	Limited	Yes
be available for testing over a 2-3 year period	Yes	Yes	Maybe	Yes	Yes
be suitable for application in full text resources, databases of references and abstracts in the health science disciplines	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
have clear policies and permissions regarding data collection behaviours and privacy practices	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
support the responsible conduct of research, such as providing functionalities supporting methodological transparency, reproducibility and good citation practice, including documentation of the applied search and ranking/clustering algorithms.	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Carrot2 is a really interesting application, but the usability of the desktop version for library users is too advanced. Further, the lack of control over the search and reference management functionalities in the webversion is problematic. The latter applies to Semantic Search and Microsoft Academic as well. For our users at the library, the search is typically the foundational method to find empirical data and as such must be transparent and documentable. We would though suggest Carrot2 workbench is further tested in the DataLabs, as this could add to the portfolio of visualization tools such as VosViewer and Gephi. The discovery functionalities in Semantic Scholar and Microsoft Academic are very similar to existing library databases such as Ovid and lack the innovation experience provided by Iris.ai and Yewno. ATherefore, two AI-powered search software fulfill our requirements. These are Iris.ai and Yewno.

Next steps are described below:

- Preliminary contact to the provider of the software Iris.ai and Yewno to assess pricing, functionality and test period.
- Build an experimental model and make a design for testing Iris.ai and Yewno.
- Test the model with information specialists before approaching researcher and students for further testing.

References

Arguello, J. (2017). Aggregated Search. *Found. Trends Inf. Retr.* 10, 5 (6 3 2017), 365–502.
DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1561/15000000052>

Florez, K (2019, February 15). What is AI-powered search? [Blog] Retrieved from:
<https://lucidworks.com/post/what-is-ai-powered-search/>

Iris.ai (2018a, November 27). Modelling topics for the focus tool. [Webpage]. Retrieved from:
<https://help.iris.ai/dive-into-the-tech/modelling-topics-for-the-focus-tool/>

Iris.ai. (2018b, November 27). Iris.ai: your research assistant. [Webpage] Retrieved from: <https://iris.ai/>

Pecánek, M. (2020, June 11). What is semantic search? How it impacts SEO. [Blog]. Retrieved from:
<https://ahrefs.com/blog/semantic-search/>

